

Healthy Paranoia - Simple Protection for End-User

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2016 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160908> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Nothing is more depressing than the *lack of power*. The feeling that you can't protect and defend yourself. To resolve this issue you may choose one of two possible paths: Either you start to ignore the importance of things or you try to handle them properly.

Privacy and security on the Internet worries a lot of people. These worries are fueled by *complexity* of computers and network technologies. But security and privacy is not something absolute. It is like a dimming light: It ranges from dark to bright. If an attacker has an *economical advantage* [1] of taking over a computer depends on the dim level of the target. I am sure that there are quick and easy possibilities to improve security without understanding the underlying technologies in depth.

3. Three simple tips

The three most important, and even easiest, steps to increase the security and privacy on the Internet are:

- Do not *memorize your passwords* [2]
- Installation of browser extensions
 - *uBlock Origin* [3], to defend against malvertising campaigns
 - *Ghostery* [4], to defend against tracking mechanism
 - *HTTPS Everywhere* [5], to make eavesdropping a lot harder
 - *Disable WebRTC für Mozilla Firefox* [6] or *WebRTC Leak Prevent for Google Chrome* [7] because of technical reasons which might not be easy to *understand* [8]
- Multiple-factor authentication for mail services

4. Multi-factor Authentication

Multi-factor authentication extends the traditional authentication by username/password. It adds another authentication mechanism. Even if the password is written on a wall an attacker might not be able to login properly because of this added factor.

The additional effort for a user is nearly inexistent. After a successful authentication the handling of the application remains the very same like before. Just in some cases some additional verification steps might be necessary.

If an attacker is able to gain access to the secret password, the *abuse of the mail account* [9] is prevented. Who might be interested in your emails? Usually just a few. But may somebody reset the passwords of other accounts with the help of your mail account? Indeed!

Therefore let's add multi-factor authentication to your mail accounts:

- *Gmail* [10]
- *Yahoo* [11]
- *Apple* [12]
- *mail.ru* [13]
- *Yandex* [14]
- *Outlook.com* [15]
- *Posteo.de* [16]

Your mail service provider is not listed here? Check twofactorauth.org [17] to see if your partner might support such a solution anyway.

Multi-factor authentication is available for other services like *Facebook* [18], *Twitter* [19] and *LinkedIn* [20]. The same level of security is guaranteed for these services. But the primary act of adding multi-factor authentication shall focus on your mail account.

5. External Links

- [1] <http://krebsonsecurity.com/2012/10/the-scrap-value-of-a-hacked-pc-revisited/>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151008>
- [3] <https://www.google.ch/webhp?q=ublock%20origin>
- [4] <https://www.ghostery.com/>
- [5] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150514>
- [6] <https://addons.mozilla.org/en-US/firefox/addon/happy->

bonobo-disable-webrtc/?src=search

[7] <https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/webrtc-leak-prevent/eiadekoaikjlgdbkbfiejlgfdalml?hl=en>

[8] <https://kowabit.de/webbrowser-vor-webrtc-schuetzen/>

[9] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160825>

[10] <http://accounts.google.com/SmsAuthConfig>

[11] <https://login.yahoo.com/account/security>

[12] <https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT204915>

[13] <https://help.mail.ru/enmail-help/settings/2auth>

[14] <https://yandex.com/promo/2fa>

[15] [https://support.microsoft.com/en-](https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/help/12408/microsoft-account-about-two-step-)

[us/help/12408/microsoft-account-about-two-step-](https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/help/12408/microsoft-account-about-two-step-)

verification

[16] <https://posteo.de/hilfe/was-ist-die-zwei-faktor-authentifizierung-und-wie-richte-ich-sie-ein>

[17] <https://twofactorauth.org/>

[18] [https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook-](https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook-engineering/introducing-login-approvals/10150172618258920/)

[engineering/introducing-login-](https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook-engineering/introducing-login-approvals/10150172618258920/)

[approvals/10150172618258920/](https://www.facebook.com/notes/facebook-engineering/introducing-login-approvals/10150172618258920/)

[19] [https://blog.twitter.com/2013/getting-started-with-](https://blog.twitter.com/2013/getting-started-with-login-verification)

[login-verification](https://blog.twitter.com/2013/getting-started-with-login-verification)

[20] [https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/544/tu-](https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/544/tu)

[ming-two-step-verification-on-and-off](https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/544/tu)